

SILVER-CATALYSED REDUCTION OF PERSULPHATE BY FORMIC ACID

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Silver-catalysed reduction of persulphate by formic acid has been studied by following the kinetics iodometrically. The reaction is of first order in persulphate and independent of the concentration of formic acid. Salt-effect could not be determined owing to the specific influence of the ions. Nitrate ion greatly inhibits the reaction. Frequency factor has been calculated and a mechanism suggested. A white turbidity is obtained if sodium or potassium formate is employed in place of formic acid.

Uncatalysed reduction of persulphate by sodium formate (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1953, 202, 198) and formic acid (unpublished) has been studied by Srivastava and Ghosh. Silver ion was reported to be a good catalyst, but no systematic and detailed study was made by them. We have carried out the investigations with potassium and sodium formates and found the first order constants to decrease with time during any run, and a white turbidity to appear in the reaction mixture, which ultimately turned grey. This occurred as a result of the reduction of silver nitrate by formate. However, there appeared little or no turbidity on employing formic acid in presence of sulphuric acid, the concentration of silver ion being kept low. The kinetics were followed by estimating the persulphate iodometrically by the method of Szabo *et al.* (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1952, 135, 269).

A preliminary study indicated that the persulphate reacted only very slowly with the formate or formic acid in absence of silver. The course of reaction was followed by two methods. In one of them, using formate, the acid obtained by the reduction of persulphate was estimated by a standard alkali and in the other, using both formate and formic acid, persulphate was estimated iodometrically (*loc.cit.*). We failed to observe any reaction within 40 minutes at 35° by the second method, whereas by the first method, only approximately 1/20 persulphate reacted in the same period. Also, we tried to study the silver-catalysed reaction by estimating the acid, but no regular and reproducible results were obtained. It appears that the method of estimating the acid is not free from objection.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of B. D. H.-A. R. or E. Merck-G.R. quality. All the vessels and the apparatus used in this investigation were of Jena glass and the medium of reaction was redistilled water from a pyrex vessel. Stock solutions of formic acid and silver nitrate were prepared in redistilled water and the acid was standardised by NaOH.

Perculphate solution was always freshly prepared by direct weighing and its concentration checked by Eckardt's method (*Chem. News*, 1900, 81, 38).

The reaction was studied at 35° in a thermostat. Silver nitrate was added in the end to start the reaction. The total volume of the reaction mixture was 100 c.c. The reaction mixture (5 c.c.) was taken out at suitable intervals of time and added to a beaker containing 2.5 c.c. of 60% KI, 10 c.c. of HCl (~ 3*N*) and 1 c.c. of the catalyst. The catalyst was prepared by dissolving 2.59 g. of A. R. ferrous ammonium sulphate and 9.82 g. of A.R. copper sulphate in 500 c.c. of distilled water. HCl checked the reaction by precipitating silver as chloride, and unchanged persulphate and copper sulphate liberated iodine. Moreover, the chloride ions inhibited the uncatalysed reaction, as reported by Srivastava and Ghosh (*loc.cit.*). The iodine was titrated against 0.04*N* sodium thiosulphate from a microburette. A blank was also run with the catalyst and all other reactants, excepting the persulphate and the blank, were subtracted from the reading of the microburette. There was no significant reaction between liberated iodine and formic acid within the time for which the titration was performed.

DISCUSSION

The first order constants were calculated from the relation :

$$k = (2.303/t) \times (1/C_{Ag^+}) \times (\log a/a-x) \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where 'a' and 'a-x' are the concentrations of persulphate initially and after time 't', and C_{Ag^+} is the concentration of the catalyst.

Some of the results are shown in Fig. 1 where $\log a/a-x$ has been plotted against time. No straight line is obtained in case of sodium formate. The first order constants decrease with time, as mentioned earlier. Gradual decrease of concentration of the catalyst by reduction may be one reason for this. Another reason may be the progressive formation of sulphuric acid in the reaction mixture, which slows down the reaction. This may easily be concluded from the other curves where straight lines are obtained and where the slope of these lines is less than that in the case of sodium formate. We have therefore employed formic acid in place of sodium formate, and also sulphuric acid to minimise the chances of reduction of silver nitrate by formic acid. Higher concentrations of silver nitrate and formic acid could not be used for the same reason.

Further results employing formic acid with sulphuric acid are recorded in Tables I and II, which show the effect of using different concentrations of the reactants.

TABLE I

HCOOH = 0.2M. H₂SO₄ = 0.1M. AgNO₃ = 0.001M.

Time.	0.02M-K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ .		0.03M-K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ .		0.04M-K ₂ S ₂ O ₈ .	
	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	k.	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	k.	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	k.
0 min.	4.98 c.c.	...	7.51 c.c.	...	10.04 c.c.	...
10	4.40	12.37	...	...	8.90	12.04
20	4.06	10.21	6.00	11.21	8.02	11.23
30	3.66	10.27	5.44	10.74	7.28	10.72
40	3.30	10.29	4.88	10.77	6.58	10.56
50	...	...	4.38	10.78	5.98	10.36
60	2.70	10.14	3.96	10.68	5.38	10.40
70	2.44	10.19	3.54	10.74	4.80	10.54
80	2.20	10.21	3.20	10.67	4.46	10.15
90	2.00	10.14	2.94	10.42	4.04	10.12
100	1.80	10.17	2.66	10.48	3.60	10.27
110	1.62	10.21	2.34	10.60	3.28	10.17
120	1.48	10.11	2.12	10.55	2.98	10.13
Average		10.20		10.64		10.34

TABLE II

K₂S₂O₈ = 0.02M. H₂SO₄ = 0.1M. AgNO₃ = 0.001M.

Time.	0.2M-HCOOH.		0.1M-HCOOH.		0.05M-HCOOH.		0.02M-HCOOH.		0.01M-HCOOH.	
	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	k.	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	k.	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	k.	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	k.	Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ .	k.
0 min.	4.98 c.c.	...	5.20 c.c.	...	5.02 c.c.	...	5.02 c.c.	...	5.02 c.c.	...
10	4.40	12.37	...	...	4.44	12.27	4.56	10.39	4.56	10.39
20	4.06	10.21	4.04	12.62	3.98	10.86	...	...	4.30	9.74
30	3.66	10.27	3.60	10.18	3.64	10.72	3.84	8.93	3.98	7.74
40	3.30	10.29	3.26	10.03	3.36	10.04	3.54	8.73	3.70	7.63
50	...	...	2.98	10.43	3.04	10.03	3.26	8.64	...	...
60	2.70	10.14	2.72	10.20	2.74	10.09	3.00	8.58	3.20	7.51
70	2.44	10.19	2.52	10.35	2.50	9.96	2.76	8.54	2.98	7.45
80	2.20	10.21	2.24	10.08	2.28	9.86	2.56	8.36	2.80	7.29
90	2.00	10.14	2.04	10.43	...	...	2.38	8.29	2.62	7.23
100	1.80	10.17	1.88	10.15	1.84	10.04	2.22	8.16	2.46	7.13
110	1.62	10.21	1.64	10.17	1.68	9.95	...	...	...	...
120	1.48	10.11	1.48	10.18	1.54	9.85	...	...	...	...
Average		10.20		10.22		10.11				

The reaction is thus first order in persulphate and independent of the concentration of formic acid, when in excess. With lower concentrations of formic acid, the rate constants decrease with time during the run. It appears from this that there is a step of reaction which ordinarily is fast, but becomes slow when the concentration of formic acid is low. This will be dealt with in more details when the mechanism is discussed.

The rate also depends on the concentration of silver nitrate. The rate constants were 0.00523 and 0.00266 for 0.0005M and 0.00025M concentrations of silver nitrate respectively. These constants on division by the respective concentrations of silver nitrate yield the values 10.46 and 10.66 in agreement with relation (1).

Effect of Varying the Concentration of H₂SO₄.—Fig. 2 shows the results in presence of varying amounts of H₂SO₄. The velocity constants decrease as the concentration of the acid is increased in different experiments. At lower concentrations of the acid, the constants decrease with time during any run. This further confirms that H₂SO₄ is gradually produced which increases the total concentration of the acid, causing progressive inhibiting action in the reaction. At higher concentrations of H₂SO₄, formation of the acid does not substantially increase the concentration and, hence, fairly uniform constants are obtained. It is difficult to understand the role of sulphuric acid in persulphate oxidations. It retards the rate in the silver catalysed oxidation of oxalic acid (Gupta and Ghosh, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1958, 27A, 258) and hydrogen peroxide (Srivastava and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1954, 28A, 44) as in the present case. On the other hand, it increases the rate in the catalysed oxidation of potassium oxalate (Gupta and Ghosh, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, 9, 178) and uncatalysed oxidation of oxalic acid (Srivastava and Ghosh, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1956, 208, 332). In the catalysed oxidation of arsenious acid (Gupta and Misra, unpublished), it has an optimum concentration for which the reaction is fastest, whereas in the uncatalysed oxidation (Gupta, *this Journal*, 1959, 86, 643) the acid has an irregular behaviour. This points to the fact that the mechanism of the reaction is not exactly similar in all these cases.

FIG. 2

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Specific Effect of the Ions.—Several electrolytes were employed to note the salt-effect, but it could not be determined owing to the specific influence of the ions as in other persulphate oxidation reactions. Table III records the velocity constants in presence of these electrolytes.

TABLE III

K₂S₂O₈ = 0.02M. HCOOH = 0.2M.
H₂SO₄ = 0.1M. AgNO₃ = 0.001M.

Electrolyte.	Conc.	k.
...	...	10.20
K ₂ SO ₄	0.250 M	6.05
K ₂ SO ₄	0.125	6.25
K ₂ SO ₄	0.050	8.81
MgSO ₄	0.500	7.44
MgSO ₄	0.250	7.64
MgSO ₄	0.050	8.08
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.250	9.13
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	0.125	9.75

TABLE IV

Conditions are the same as in Table III.

Electrolyte.	Conc.	k.
...	...	10.20
KNO ₃	0.250 M	1.96
KNO ₃	0.125	2.76
NH ₄ NO ₃	0.250	2.58
NH ₄ NO ₃	0.125	3.61
NaNO ₃	0.250	2.36
NaNO ₃	0.125	3.33
HNO ₃	0.100	3.07
HNO ₃	0.010	8.44

No specific relationship is obtained by plotting μ or $\sqrt{\mu}$ against k or $\log k$. It appears from Table III that K^+ , Mg^{2+} and NH_4^+ as also SO_4^{2-} have inhibiting action on this reaction. Table IV records the constants in presence of nitrates.

Nitrate is found to inhibit the reaction to a great extent. The same behaviour was noted by Gupta and Ghosh (*loc.cit.*) in the silver-catalysed oxidation of oxalate. On the other hand, in the oxidation of arsenious acid, both catalysed and uncatalysed (*loc.cit.*), it is reported to be a good catalysing ion. This difference in behaviour must be accounted for by different reaction mechanisms of these oxidations. However, it is clear from Tables III and IV that K^+ , Na^+ and NH_4^+ have less inhibiting action than the nitrate ion.

Reaction in presence of Sodium Acetate.—Table V records the rate constants at different concentrations of sodium acetate and acetic acid. It has an irregular behaviour as in the oxidation of arsenious acid (*loc.cit.*). It appears that acetate ion accelerates, and sodium ion and undissociated molecule of sodium acetate retard the rate, and that the combined effect of these makes the reaction very complicated. Kinetics were followed also in absence of sulphuric acid to ascertain the exact nature of the effect of sodium acetate. The only conclusion drawn is that the acetate ion has a catalytic activity. The results in absence of sulphuric acid were irregular and varied within wide limits.

TABLE V

Conditions are the same as in Table III.

Conc. (M) ... k	Sodium acetate.					Acetic acid.	
	0.25	0.125	0.05	0.01	0.005	0.10	0.01
	6.12	12.00	18.72	12.53	21.59	13.92	16.57

Frequency Factor.—Investigations were also made at 40 and 45° to determine the energy of activation and then to calculate the frequency factor (Table VI).

TABLE VI

Conditions are the same as in Table III.

Time.	At 40°.		At 45°.	
	$Na_2S_2O_8$.	k .	$Na_2S_2O_8$.	k .
0 min.	5.00 c.c.	...	5.00 c.c.	...
10	4.06	20.83	3.74	29.04
20	3.52	17.56	2.76	29.71
30	2.94	17.71	2.04	29.92
40	2.46	17.74	1.52	29.78
50	2.08	17.55	1.20	29.21
60	1.72	17.78	0.98	27.14
70	1.44	17.78	0.80	26.21
80	1.22	17.64	...	...
90	1.02	17.67	...	...

The energy of activation and the frequency factor were found to be ≈ 20900 cal. and $\approx 1.28 \times 10^{11}$ litres/mole/sec. respectively. The rate constants slightly decrease at 45° , probably due to slight decomposition of persulphate, liberating oxygen at this temperature, and for this reason the last few observations were ignored for calculating the average. The frequency factor must be considered only qualitative, but its order of magnitude does help one to arrive at a possible reaction mechanism. This frequency factor corresponds to the overall reaction, and it may be different for the rate-determining step.

Mechanism

The reaction is first order in persulphate and independent of the concentration of formic acid. Hence, the rate-determining step does not involve the reductant concentration as in other persulphate reactions. Salt-effect could not be determined owing to the specific influence of ions. The following mechanism is proposed for this reaction.

The existence of free radicals, SO_4^- and OH , and of higher valent silver, Ag^{3+} , is now beyond doubt (Uri, *Chem. Rev.*, 1952, 50, 375). Gupta and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) and Yost (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1926, 48, 152) have already discussed the possibility of higher valent silver in other silver-catalysed oxidations by persulphate. A comparison of the observed frequency factor with the normal value 1×10^{11} does not support the generally accepted mechanism:

If this were the rate-determining step, the observed frequency factor should have been much higher than 1×10^{11} , the reaction being between oppositely charged ions (Frost and Pearson, "Kinetics and Mechanism", Wiley, New York, 1953, p. 132). Our slow step of reaction is also between oppositely charged ions, and it has a greater value of frequency factor than the normal, because this step is preceded by an equilibrium which has a very small K , of the order of 10^{-8} or even less. The slow step (II) has a first order dependence on persulphate and has a higher value of frequency factor, as shown below.

$$\begin{aligned} -dc/dt &= k_2 [\text{Ag}^+] [\text{SO}_4^-]^2 \\ \text{but} \quad K [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] &= [\text{SO}_4^-]^2 && \text{from (I)} \\ \text{Hence} \quad -dc/dt &= k_2 \cdot K [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] [\text{Ag}^+] \\ &= k_r [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}] \\ \text{where} \quad k_r &= k_2 \cdot K [\text{Ag}^+] \end{aligned}$$

Silver-ion concentration remains constant and the slow step is thus of first order in persulphate. Experimentally determined rate constant, k , is equal to $k_r/[\text{Ag}^+]$. Hence, $k = k_2 \cdot K$ or $k_2 = k/K = 10.20/10^{-8} = 10.20 \times 10^8$ litres/mole/min.

Based on this value of k_2 , the frequency factor for the step (II) is $\approx 1.28 \times 10^{10}$ litres/mole/sec. We thus come to the conclusion that the slow step is more likely between oppositely charged ions than between persulphate and silver ions; it is between positive silver ion and a negative radical ion obtained from persulphate.

Step (II) of the mechanism is ordinarily quite fast. When, however, the concentration of formic acid is low, this step is not as fast, and some of Ag^{3+} ions react with water, producing OH, which probably does not oxidise formic acid or does so only slowly.

OH liberates iodine from potassium iodide in the iodometric analysis, thus providing higher estimated values of persulphate and decreasing velocity constants. The same behaviour was noted in the oxidation of oxalate by Gupta and Ghosh (*loc.cit.*). In fact, oxidation of oxalate and formic acid are similar in many respects. Mention has already been made of the specific influence of the ions in these two oxidations. In this connection it may be stated that the silver-catalysed oxidations of oxalate, arsenious acid and formic acid have the same order of magnitude of velocity constants, and, hence, they belong to one type as distinct from the other type of catalysed oxidations, such as those of Cr^{3+} (Yost, *loc.cit.*), VO^{3+} (Yost and Claussen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 3349), Mn^{2+} (Dekker *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, 59, 2129), Ce^{2+} (Cone, *ibid.*, 1945, 67, 78) etc. Table VII records the rate constants for these ions.

TABLE VII

Reductant.	k . (litres/mole/min.)	Temp.	Electrolyte present other than reactants.	Reference.
K-oxalate	18.58	30°	0.09 M- H_2SO_4	Gupta & Ghosh
H_3AsO_3	18.80	24°	0.10 "	Gupta & Misra
H_3AsO_3	30.54	29°	" "	Gupta & Misra
HCOOH	10.20	35°	0.10 "	"
HCOONa	11.96	35°	0.10 "	"
Mn (II)	0.45	35°	0.25 K_2SO_4	Gupta & Ghosh
Mn (II)	0.25-0.30	25°	0.10 HNO_3	Dekker <i>et al.</i>
Cr (III)	0.30-0.33	25°	0.09 H_2SO_4	Yost
VO(II)	0.30-0.36	25°	0.10 HClO_4	Yost & Claussen
Ce(II)	0.40-0.45	25°	" "	Cone
N_2H_4	0.40-0.50	25°	0.03 "	Dekker <i>et al.</i>

